

Alkaline Earth Metal Complexes. Reactions of Calcium Ions with Common Plant Acids

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Calcium complexes of citric, malic and tartaric acids and their mixed ternary ones, have been investigated by conductometric titration and elemental analysis of the isolated solid compounds. Conductometric titration data indicated the formation of binary 1 : 1 and 1 : 2 calcium-citrate, and 1 : 2 calcium-malate and -tartarate complexes. The 1 : 1 : 1 stoichiometry of the ternary calcium malatocitrate, calcium malatosuccinate, calcium tartaratocitrate, calcium tartaratomalate and calcium tartaratosuccinate, and 1 : 1 : 2 calcium malatosuccinate complexes have been indicated by such study. The 1 : 1 calcium citrate, 1 : 2 calcium-malate and -tartarate complexes have been isolated in solid state.

CALCIUM occurs in plants and animals and its reactions with naturally occurring compounds would be helpful in understanding the mechanism of absorption, transport and storage of calcium in bio-systems. In the present paper, the binary and ternary complexes of calcium with plant acids, viz. citric, malic, succinic and tartaric acids are being reported on the basis of conductometric evidences.

The specificity of tartaric acid for calcium is well known¹. Interaction of calcium with citric acid has been intensively studied in literature²⁻⁴. The complex formations of alkaline earth cations with malic, citric and tartaric acids have been reported in literature⁵⁻⁷. We have isolated 1 : 1 calcium-citrate, 1 : 2 calcium-malate and -tartarate complexes. A 1 : 2 calcium-citrate complex has also been studied by conductometric titrations.

Experimental

All the neutral calcium salts were prepared by the usual methods and were tested for purity by elemental analysis. The standard acid solutions were prepared in conductivity water. The suspensions of known weights of the neutral calcium salts of citric, malic and tartaric acids in conductivity water (100 ml), were titrated conductometrically, against standard solutions of the plant acid component with the help of Systronics 303, a direct reading conductivity meter using a conductivity cell of black platinised platinum electrodes. The instrument was calibrated with standard KCl solution. After each addition of the titrant, a time period of 3 min for stirring followed by one 1 min for settling down, was allowed before taking the reading.

The solid complexes were isolated by the general method of interaction of water suspension of neutral calcium salts of the acids with an excess of the corresponding acid solutions, till a clear solution

was obtained. In case of malic acid complex, owing to the higher solubility of calcium malate, an excess of acid solution was added even beyond the visible dissolution point. The clear solutions, thus obtained, were filtered, concentrated on water-bath and crystallised. The crystals were filtered, washed with cold distilled water to remove any adhered free acid and dried in an air-oven at 100° temperature.

Results

The neutral calcium citrate, malate and tartarate salts prepared have been found to be of molecular formula $\text{Ca}_2\text{C}_{12}\text{O}_{14}\text{H}_{10}\cdot 4\text{H}_2\text{O}$, $\text{CaC}_4\text{O}_5\text{H}_4\cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$ and $\text{CaC}_4\text{O}_6\text{H}_4\cdot 4\text{H}_2\text{O}$ respectively, by elemental analysis. The results are as follows : 1 : 1 calcium citrate complex (Found : Ca, 15.23 ; C, 30.26 ; H, 3.94. $\text{Ca}(\text{C}_6\text{O}_7\text{H}_8)\cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ requires : Ca, 15.04 ; C, 27.07 ; H, 3.76%) ; 1 : 2 calcium malate complex (Found : Ca, 13.23 ; C, 27.97 ; H, 4.78. $\text{Ca}(\text{C}_4\text{O}_5\text{H}_5)_2\cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ requires Ca, 11.69 ; C, 28.07 ; H, 4.09%) ; 1 : 2 calcium tartarate complex (Found : Ca, 9.53 ; C, 27.12 ; H, 4.00. $\text{Ca}(\text{C}_4\text{O}_6\text{H}_5)_2\cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ requires : Ca, 10.69 ; C, 25.67 ; H, 3.74%).

Colour, m.p./decomp. temp. of the complexes are given in Table 1. Conductometric titration data are presented in Table 2.

Discussion

The curve of calcium citrate ($\text{Ca}_2(\text{cit})\cdot 4\text{H}_2\text{O}$)-citric acid titration showed two breaks at 1 : 1 and 1 : 4 mole ratios between calcium citrate and citric acid. These correspond to a 1 : 1 and 1 : 2 mole ratios between Ca^{2+} and cit^{3-} ions. The curves for calcium malate vs malic acid titration and calcium tartarate-tartaric acid titration showed only

TABLE 1—PHYSICAL PROPERTIES OF COMPLEXES

Compd.	Colour	Decomp. temp. °C	Colour change during decomp.	M.p. of the corresponding acid from which complexes prepared °C
Calcium citrate complex (1 : 1)	Shining white	230	Grey	
Calcium citrate complex (1 : 2)	White	155	Pale yellow	
Calcium malate complex (1 : 2)	Shining white	138-39 ^a	Pale yellow	
Calcium tartarate complex (1 : 2)	Shining white	139 ^a	Pale yellow	
Calcium malatocitrate (1 : 1 : 1)	White	235	Yellow	153 (citric)
Calcium malatosuccinate (1 : 1 : 1)	White	255	Grey	185 (succinic)
Calcium malatodisuccinate (1 : 1 : 2)	White	260	Grey	185 (succinic)
Calcium tartaratocitrate (1 : 1 : 1)	White	260	Yellow	153 (citric)
Calcium tartaraomalate (1 : 1 : 1)	White	240	Pale yellow	100 (malic)
Calcium tartaratosuccinate (1 : 1 : 1)	White	195	Yellow	185 (succinic)

Melted.

TABLE 2—CONDUCTOMETRIC TITRATION OF Ca-CITRATE, Ca-MALATE AND Ca-TARTARATE

Initial volume = 100 ml		Inflection point (ml) : Found/(Calcd.)	
Complex g	Titant	1 : 1	1 : 2
Ca-citrate 0.114	0.4 M Citric acid	0.6 (0.5)	2.2 (2.0)
Ca-malate 0.344	0.5 M Malic acid ^b	3.2 (3.6)	—
0.268	0.4 M Citric acid ^b	3.8 (3.5)	—
0.2746	0.5 M Succinic acid ^b	2.6 (2.9)	5.8 (5.8)
Ca-tartarate 0.188	0.5 M Tartaric acid	1.75 (1.45)	—
0.188	0.5 M Malic acid ^a	1.7 (1.45)	—
0.188	0.4 M Citric acid ^a	1.6 (1.8)	—
0.188	0.5 M Succinic acid ^a	1.48 (1.45)	—

 At $\alpha 32^\circ$, $\beta 30^\circ$.

one break in the vicinity of 1 : 1 mole ratio between the reactants indicating the formation of 1 : 2 calcium malate and 1 : 2 calcium tartarate complexes. In case of calcium citrate-citric acid titration, the visible dissolution of the original suspension took place between the 1st and 2nd breaks. In case of calcium malate-malic acid titration, the visible dissolution took place before the lone break point. In calcium tartarate-tartaric acid titration, the visible dissolution took place beyond the break point. Thus, conductometric titrations provided evidence of various complexes, viz. 1 : 1 calcium citrate, 1 : 2 calcium citrate, 1 : 2 calcium malate and 1 : 2 calcium tartarate.

In all of the above titrations, the specific conductivity continued to increase with the addition of the titrant; at the break points, however, the rate of increase of specific conductivities decreased. The

volume of titrant in all the cases were so adjusted that there could not possibly be any dilution effect.

The elemental analysis of the solid compounds isolated were found to be in closer agreement to the values required for 1 : 1 calcium citrate, 1 : 2 calcium malate and 1 : 2 calcium tartarate complexes together with two molecules of water in each case. The water molecules seem to be strongly associated to the metal ions, for they could be released at temperatures much higher than 100° . The m.p./decomp. temp. of the complexes (Table 1) as compared to those of the starting ingredients, suggest them to be genuine compounds and not the stoichiometric mixtures of the starting ingredients. Our attempts to isolate the 1 : 2 calcium citrate complex, as shown by conductometry, have met with failure. However, the m.p. (155°) of a dry residue, obtained by evaporating a solution containing calcium citrate and citric acid in 1 : 4 molar ratio to dryness was 2° higher than the m.p. of citric acid (153°), indicating, thus, the dry residue to be a genuine compound and not the mixture of calcium citrate and citric acid. The dry residue on treatment with absolute ethanol yielded the 1 : 1 calcium citrate complex. Thus, our observations suggest the formation of 1 : 1 calcium citrate, 1 : 2 calcium malate and 1 : 2 calcium tartarate complexes in aqueous solution and their isolability in the solid state; and a 1 : 2 calcium citrate complex, existing perhaps, only in aqueous solution.

In the titrations carried out for mixed ligand ternary complexes, the initially taken suspension ultimately went into solutions indicating non-replacement chemical interactions between the reactants. A replacement reaction under the experimental conditions would have resulted in the precipitation of the calcium salt of the titrant acid. For comparative purpose a titration in which there would be a replacement, was also carried out, e.g. calcium malate was titrated against tartaric acid. The suspension of calcium malate initially went into solution but was immediately followed by the precipitation of calcium tartarate (replacement). The plots for the titrations, calcium malate vs citric

acid, calcium tartarate vs citric, malic and succinic acids showed only one break in the vicinity of 1 : 1 mole ratio between the neutral calcium salt and the titrant free acid, suggesting a 1 : 1 complexation between the reactants. The plot for calcium malate against succinic acid titration showed two breaks at 1 : 1 and 1 : 2 mole ratio between the reactants suggesting a 1 : 1 and 1 : 2 complexation between calcium malate and succinic acid. Since the neutral calcium malate and tartarate have a 1 : 1 stoichiometry between the metal ion and the carboxylate anion in them, the complexes corresponding to the 1 : 1 break, seem to have a 1 : 1 : 1 stoichiometry among the calcium ions and the two different acid anions. The 1 : 2 break in calcium malate vs succinic acid titration suggests a complex of 1 : 1 : 2 stoichiometry among the calcium ions, malic acid and succinic acid, respectively. In the titrations with calcium malate, the visible dissolution of the original suspension took place before the break points, whereas in titrations with calcium tartarate, the visible dissolution took place beyond the break points. Complexation as the primary factor for 1 : 1 break in case of titrations of calcium tartarate with different acids has been mentioned earlier. In the case of replacement titration (calcium malate vs tartaric acid), the specific conductivity initially increased with the addition of the titrant, followed by visible dissolution. But around the 1 : 1 mole ratio between the reactants, the precipitation of calcium tartarate started with the decreased in specific conductivity till the replacement was complete. Beyond this, calcium tartarate formed, started to dissolve slowly with further addition of the titrant (tartaric acid) with a gradual increase in specific conductivity, resulting roughly in a V-shaped curve. Thus various complexes indicated

are (i) calcium malatocitrate (1 : 1 : 1), (ii) calcium malatosuccinate (1 : 1 : 1), (iii) calcium malatodisuccinate (1 : 1 : 2), (iv) calcium tartaratocitrate (1 : 1 : 1), (v) calcium tartaratomalate (1 : 1 : 1) and (vi) calcium tartaratosuccinate (1 : 1 : 1).

The mixed ligand ternary complexes could not be isolated in the solid state, suggesting thus, their probable existence only in aqueous solution. However, the neutral calcium salts and the free acid solutions were mixed in exact mole ratios corresponding to the conductometric breaks. The clear solutions thus obtained were evaporated to dryness on water-bath. The melting/decomposition temperatures of these dry residues (Table 1) have generally been found to be higher than the m.p./decom. temp. of the free acids from which they were prepared, supporting conclusions drawn from conductometric titrations.

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References

1. R. J. P. WILLIAMS, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1952, 3770.
2. EULER and BOLIN, *Z. Phys. Chem.*, 1909, 61, 1.
3. E. SHORR, T. P. ALAMY, M. H. SLOAN, H. TAUSKY and V. TOSCANI, *Science*, 1942, 96, 587.
4. J. MUSS and H. LEBEL, *Medd*, 1936, 13, 17.
5. R. K. CANNAS and A. KIBRICK, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1938, 60, 2314.
6. N. JOSEPH, *J. Biol. Chem.*, 1946, 164, 529.
7. M. BOBTELSKY and J. JORDAN *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1945, 67, 1824.
8. F. DEFRANCESCO and C. DEFRANCESCO, *Rev. Soc. Ital. Sci. Aliment*, 1978, 7, 381.